

Template scripts for gene prediction and annotation

List of programs

We list the main programs used for gene prediction and annotation below. The links were tested on June 2, 2021.

- BRAKER v2.1.2: <https://github.com/Gaius-Augustus/BRAKER>
- GeneMark-ET/EP+ v4.38: <http://exon.gatech.edu/GeneMark/>
- AUGUSTUS v.3.3.2: <https://github.com/Gaius-Augustus/Augustus>
- BLAST v.2.9.0+: <ftp://ftp.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/blast/executables/blast+>
- exonerate v2.4.0ls: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/about/vertebrate-genomics/software/exonerate>
- GMAP v2021.03.08: <https://github.com/juliangehring/GMAP-GSNAP>
- BLAT v36x2: http://hgdownload.soe.ucsc.edu/downloads.html#source_downloads

Reading the template scripts

Template scripts have placeholders indicated within smaller than (<) and greater than (>) signs. For example, you should replace `</path/to/working/directory>` with the path to your working directory. Other comments start with a pound sign (#).

The following scripts were tested on Red Hat Enterprise Linux 7.5 using the UNC Charlotte's research clusters (<https://oneit.uncc.edu/urc/research-clusters>).

BRAKER's PBS execution script

The following template script was used to execute BRAKER using the PBS job scheduler: ``

#!/bin/bash

PBS -l walltime=168:00:00

PBS -l nodes=1:ppn=64

PBS -l mem=2000GB

PBS -N

PBS -j oe

PBS -q

IFS=\$'\n' set -eu umask 007 shopt -s nullglob

Define variables:

*MD= AUGUSTUSCONFIG= GENEMARK=gmespetap SPECIES=strongylocentrotuspurpuratus
REFERENCE= ALIGNMENT= TRANSCRIPTOME EVIDENCE= THREADS=64*

Change to the working directory:

cd \${MD}

The modules below may not be available in your system, but this can be used as a list of dependencies required to run the command line below:

module load anaconda3 module load module load augustus/3.3.2 module load genemark/4.38

module load blast/2.5.0+ module load braker

BRAKER's command line:

```
braker.pl --AUGUSTUSCONFIGPATH=${AUGUSTUSCONFIG} --  
GENEMARKPATH=${GENEMARK} --species=${SPECIES} --genome=${REFERENCE} --  
bam=${ALIGNMENT} --hints=${TRANSCRIPTOME_EVIDENCE} --filterOutShort --cores  
${THREADS} --overwrite --skipAllTraining ``
```

Note that the shebang of the script above assumes that `bash` is in `/bin/`.

BLAST's execution command

The following template command line was used to create BLAST's Bash scripts:

```
blastx -query </path/to/fasta> -db </name/of/database> -out </path/to/out  
put/file> -num_threads <number of threads> -outfmt 6
```

Note that the command line above assumes that you have a database prepared with `makeblastdb`.

Mapping transcripts to genomic scaffolds

We mapped the scaffolds from the brittle star, *Ophioderma brevispinum*, transcriptome (from Mashanov et al. 2020; DOI: [10.1371/journal.pone.0232981](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0232981)) to its draft genome assembly.

We also mapped the cDNA from the purple sea urchin, *Strongylocentrotus purpuratus* (file `Strongylocentrotus_purpuratus.Spur_5.0.cdna.all.fa`), available from https://metazoa.ensembl.org/Strongylocentrotus_purpuratus), to the draft genome of the brittle star, *Ophioderma brevispinum*.

We used BLAT v. 36x2, Exonerate v2.4.0ls, and GMAP v2021-03-08, as described below.

BLAT's SLURM script

```

#!/bin/bash

#SBATCH --partition=<partition>
#SBATCH --job-name=<name>
#SBATCH --nodes=1
#SBATCH --ntasks-per-node=36
#SBATCH --mem=375gb
#SBATCH --time=24:00:00

echo "======"
echo "Start Time : $(date)"
echo "Submit Dir : $SLURM_SUBMIT_DIR"
echo "Job ID/Name : $SLURM_JOBID / $SLURM_JOB_NAME"
echo "Node List : $SLURM_JOB_NODELIST"
echo "Num Tasks : $SLURM_NTASKS total [$SLURM_NNODES nodes @ $SLURM_CPUS_ON_NODE CPUs/node]"
echo "======"
echo ""

blat -t=dna -q=rna -mask=lower -out=blast8 </path/to/genome/data/in/fasta
> </path/to/cdna/data/in/fasta> <output>

echo ""
echo "======"
echo "End Time : $(date)"
echo "======"

```

GMAP's SLURM script

Create the genome database

```

#!/bin/bash

#SBATCH --partition=<partition>
#SBATCH --job-name=<name>
#SBATCH --nodes=1
#SBATCH --ntasks-per-node=36
#SBATCH --mem=375gb
#SBATCH --time=24:00:00

echo "======"
echo "Start Time : $(date)"
echo "Submit Dir : $SLURM_SUBMIT_DIR"
echo "Job ID/Name : $SLURM_JOBID / $SLURM_JOB_NAME"
echo "Node List : $SLURM_JOB_NODELIST"
echo "Num Tasks : $SLURM_NTASKS total [$SLURM_NNODES nodes @ $SLURM_CPU
S_ON_NODE CPUs/node]"
echo "======"
echo ""

gmap_build -t 34 -k 15 --dir </path/to/destination/directory> --genomedb
<genome_name> </path/to/genome/fasta/file>

echo ""
echo "======"
echo "End Time : $(date)"
echo "======"

```

Align

```

#!/bin/bash

#SBATCH --partition=<partition>
#SBATCH --job-name=<name>
#SBATCH --nodes=1
#SBATCH --ntasks-per-node=36
#SBATCH --mem=375gb
#SBATCH --time=24:00:00

echo "======"
echo "Start Time : $(date)"
echo "Submit Dir : $SLURM_SUBMIT_DIR"
echo "Job ID/Name : $SLURM_JOBID / $SLURM_JOB_NAME"
echo "Node List : $SLURM_JOB_NODELIST"
echo "Num Tasks : $SLURM_NTASKS total [$SLURM_NNODES nodes @ $SLURM_CPUS_ON_NODE CPUs/node]"
echo "======"
echo ""

# Note that the command below expects a genome database (see script above
).

gmap \
  -D </path/to/the/working/directory> \
  -d </name/of/the/genome/database> \
  -t 32 \
  -k 15 \
  -B 4 \
  </path/to/cdna/data/in/fasta> > <output> 2> <error>

echo ""
echo "======"
echo "End Time : $(date)"
echo "======"

```

Exonerate's SLURM script

```

#!/bin/bash

#SBATCH --partition=<partition>
#SBATCH --job-name=<name>
#SBATCH --nodes=1
#SBATCH --ntasks-per-node=<cpus>
#SBATCH --mem=1000gb

```

```

#SBATCH --time=200:00:00

echo "======"
echo "Start Time : $(date)"
echo "Submit Dir : $SLURM_SUBMIT_DIR"
echo "Job ID/Name : $SLURM_JOBID / $SLURM_JOB_NAME"
echo "Node List : $SLURM_JOB_NODELIST"
echo "Num Tasks : $SLURM_NTASKS total [$SLURM_NNODES nodes @ $SLURM_CPUS_ON_NODE CPUs/node]"
echo "======"
echo ""

module load exonerate/2.4.0
module list

export QR1=</path/to/fasta/file>
export QR2=</path/to/fasta/file>
export SCF=</path/to/fasta/file>
export WDR=</path/to/working/directory>

for i in {1..100} ; do
FILE="exonerate_Sp_${i}.out"
if [ -f "${FILE}" ]; then
printf "! ${FILE} exists (skipping).\n"
else
printf ":-) ${FILE} does not exist (exonerating).\n"
exonerate --percent 75 --dpmemory 500000 --fsmmemory 500000 --softmasktar
get yes --verbose 1 --showalignment no --showvulgar no --showsugar no --s
howcigar no --showtargetgff yes --model est2genome --querychunkid ${i} --
querychunktotal 100 ${QR2} ${SCF} > exonerate_Sp_${i}.out 2> exonerate_Sp
_${i}.err
wait
fi
printf "\n//\n"
done

echo ""
echo "======"
echo "End Time : $(date)"
echo "======"

```

